

Household Enrolment CRF

#	Question	Variable
1	Today's date	DD/MM/YYYY
2	Household ID	
Section 1: Household Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria		
3	Does the household lie within the boundaries of the study sites?	Yes No (exclude)
4	Can the household provide the minimum number of samples?	Yes No (exclude)
Section 2: Household Demographics and Economic Data		
5	Including yourself, how many adults (>16) live in the household?	
6	How many 5-15-year-olds?	
7	How many 2-5-year-olds?	
8	How many <2-year-olds?	
9	Who is the head of household?	Respondent is head of household (self) Mother Father Grandparent Sibling Spouse Child Other relative
10	What is the name of the Head of Household?	
11	Please think about the person who is the head of your household. It might be you, or it may be someone else. What is the Job status of the head of the household?	Paid employee Paid domestic worker Self employed Unemployed Unpaid family worker Student Other (specify)
12	Please think about the person who is the head of your household. It might be you, or it may be someone else. What is the occupation of the head of household?	Agriculture Domestic service Unskilled manual Skilled manual Sales and service Clerical Technical / managerial

		Healthcare Other Professional Student Other (specify)
13	Please think about the person who is the head of your household. It might be you, or it may be someone else. What is the date of birth of the head of household?	DD/MM/YYYY
14	If date of birth unknown, what is the age of the head of household (in years)?	_____yrs
15	Please think about the person who is the head of your household. It might be you, or it may be someone else. What is the highest educational qualification the household head has acquired?	None PSLC JCE MSCE Non-University Diploma University Diploma/Degree Postgraduate Degree
16	What does the head of your household sleep on?	Bed and Mattress Bed & Mattress (GRASS) Bed alone Mattress on floor Mattress (GRASS) on floor Cloth / Sack on floor Floor (Nothing Else) Other (specify)
17	How many people in your house receive a regular income?	One (respondents) Two Three Four Five More than 5
18	What on average is your household monthly income (in local currency)?	
19	What are your top 5 key expenditures? Select 5 responses	Food Education Rent Transport Phone Units Utility bills Wages for household workers/agriculture workers Clothes Healthcare Farming/animal costs Other (specify)

20	Does your household own the following? <i>(select for each)</i> A. A Tape or CD/DVD player or a HiFi B. An upholstered chair (armchair) or sofa set C. An iron for pressing clothes.	Yes No
21	Do you, either by yourself or together with another household member or someone outside your household, currently have an account at a bank, credit union, micro finance institution, village savings organization, or another financial institution?	Yes No
22	Do you own or rent the house?	Own Rent Other (specify)
23	How many households are within the compound?	One (respondents) Two Three Four Five More than 5
24	How many of the household members attend a CBCC?	0 (go to Q25) Number _____
24a	What CCBCs do they attend?	
25	How many members of the household attend primary school?	0 (go to Q26) Number _____
25a	Name of schools(s)	
26	How many members of the household attend secondary school?	0 (go to Q27) Number _____
26a	Name of secondary school(s)	
27	Does anyone in the house own any of the following? <i>(select for each)</i> A. Car or Truck B. Radio C. Cell phone D. Television E. Bicycle F. Refrigerator	Yes No

	G. Bed	
28	During the past month how often have you had problems getting the food that you need?	Never Sometimes Often Always
29	In the last 2 weeks, has an adult in your household skipped a meal or eaten less in order for there to be enough food?	Yes No
30	Does anyone in your household have health insurance?	Yes No
Section 3: Household Visitors		
31	Have you had any visitors sleeping in the house who do not normally stay with you, in the last month?	Yes No (go to Q32)
31a	How many visitors have you had?	
<i>For each visitor fill in Q31ai-Q31aiii</i>		
31ai	What is their relationship to the family?	Grandparent Mother or Father Brother or Sister Cousin Aunty or Uncle Son or Daughter Grandson or granddaughter Friend Employee Stranger
31aii	What is their sex?	Male Female Prefer not to say
31aiii	What is their age?	_____ yrs
32	Imagine six steps, where on the bottom, the first step, stand the poorest people, and on the highest step, the sixth, stand the rich. SHOW THE PICTURE OF THE STEPS. On which step are you today?	
Section 4: Structural and WASH Data		
33	How many rooms does your house have?	
34	House wall construction	Unbaked bricks Baked bricks Cement / concrete

		Other (specify)
35	House roof construction	Metal Thatch Sod Rustic mat Palm/bamboo Other (specify)
36	House floor finish	Cement Tile Carpet Wood Sand/soil Other (Specify)
37	Do you have a toilet?	No toilet (go to Q38) Home: Flush/pour flush toilet to main sewer Home: Flush/pour flush toilet to septic tank Home: Pit latrine with slab and cover Home: Pit latrine with slab only Home: Pit latrine with soil/wood floor Home: Composting toilet Home: Bucket Home: Other (specify) Public toilet (go to Q38) Other (specify)
37a	Does your toilet ever flood?	Yes No
37b	Do you share this toilet with others that are not members of your household?	Yes No
37c	How many households share this toilet?	
38	Do members of the household ever openly defecate near the household?	Never A few times a year A few times a month At least once a week Most days
38a	Which members of the household do this?	Mother Father Grandparent Sibling Self Spouse Child Other relative

39	If you are away from home (e.g., in the market) and need to use the toilet where would you go?	Wait till I get home Use public toilet Urinate/defaecate in the open Borrow a toilet close by Other (specify)
40	Are there public toilets available in your area?	Yes No (go to Q41)
40a	Where are they?	
41	Do you or your family members ever use the public toilet?	Yes No
42	Do you have any children who wear nappies/cloths?	Yes No
42a	Where do you dispose of the faeces content of these cloths/nappies?	Disposable nappies collected Disposable nappies burned Disposable nappies thrown in pit or elsewhere Washable nappies/cloth – faeces in toilet Washable nappies/cloth – faeces washed off in bucket Other (specify)
42b	If washable cloths where and how are these washed?	
43	What is your drinking water source?	Bottled Piped into dwelling Piped outside dwelling Public tap / Standpipe Tube well / borehole Tube well with powered pump Cart with small tank / Drum Unprotected well / spring Rainwater collection "Surface water from river, lake or pond " Other (specify)
44	Is the water you drink in the house safe to drink?	Yes No
45	Is the household drinking water ever treated?	Yes No (go to Q46)
45a	How is it treated?	Boiled Chlorination Covered (this is perceived by many as a treatment) Filtered Solar disinfection Other (specify)
45b	How often is it treated?	Daily Weekly When I can afford to

		When there is cholera When I have time No specified time
46	How long does it take to access your drinking water source?	On premises Less than 30mins More than 30mins Days
47	Is the water source you use for washing utensils different from the drinking water source?	Yes No
48	What is the water source for washing cooking utensils?	Bottled Piped into dwelling Piped outside dwelling Public tap / Standpipe Tube well / borehole Tube well with powered pump Cart with small tank / Drum Unprotected well / spring Rainwater collection "Surface water from river, lake or pond " Other (specify)
49	What is the main source of water for bathing?	Bottled Piped into dwelling Piped outside dwelling Public tap / Standpipe Tube well / borehole Tube well with powered pump Cart with small tank / Drum Unprotected well / spring Rainwater collection "Surface water from river, lake or pond " Other (specify)
50	If different from the drinking water source, how long does it take you to access water for bathing?	On premises Less than 30mins More than 30mins Days Weeks
51	Where do you bath?	Bathing room (exterior) Bathing room (interior) Latrine No bathroom Other (specify)
52	When do you normally wash your hands?	Before eating Before feeding child Before preparing food After toilet After cleaning child nappy

		<p>After eating</p> <p>After working outside</p> <p>When they look dirty</p> <p>Other (specify)</p>
53	Where do you wash your hands at these times?	<p>At tap inside house with piped water</p> <p>At tap outside house with piped water</p> <p>Bottle/tippy tap next to toilet</p> <p>Bottle/tippy tap next to kitchen/cooking area</p> <p>Basin with water (hand dipping) at house</p> <p>Jug with water (pouring over hands) at house</p> <p>Other (specify)</p>
54	What is the source of fuel for cooking?	<p>Electricity</p> <p>Gas (any)</p> <p>Kerosene</p> <p>Charcoal</p> <p>Coal</p> <p>Wood</p> <p>Animal manure</p> <p>Other (specify)</p>
55	Do you have lights?	<p>Yes, electric lights</p> <p>Yes, solar powered lights</p> <p>Yes, gas powered lights</p> <p>No</p>
56	Do you have electricity in the house?	<p>Yes, mains electricity</p> <p>Yes, solar electricity</p> <p>Yes, fuel-based generator electricity</p> <p>No</p>
57	Is there any standing water around the house? (e.g., accumulation of rainwater or poor drainage)	<p>Yes</p> <p>No</p>
57a	Do children play or go into this standing water?	<p>Yes</p> <p>No</p>
57b	Do animals go into this standing water?	<p>Yes</p> <p>No</p>
58	Does the area around the house flood at any time?	<p>Yes</p> <p>No</p>
58a	How often does it flood?	<p>Once a year</p> <p>Up to five times a year</p> <p>Up to 10 times a year</p> <p>More than 10 times a year</p> <p>Every time it rains</p>

		Only after heavy rains
59	Do children in your household ever play or go into the drains around your household area to play or pick-up items?	Yes No
60	Do adults in your household ever go into the drains around your household area to walk or pick-up items?	Yes No
61	Do children in your household ever play or come into contact with river water?	Yes No
61a	Please explain why?	Walking to school Playing with friends Bathing Washing clothes Other (specify)
62	Do adults in your household ever or come into contact with river water?	Yes No
62a	Please explain why?	Walking Bathing Washing clothes Water for household usage Irrigation for crops Use of sand/soil for business or other purposes Other (specify)
Food and Hygiene Data		
63	How often do household members eat the following? A. Beef B. Pork C. Chicken D. Other meat	Never Less than once a week About once a week Several times a week Daily
64	How often do household members eat the following? A. Salad/raw vegetables from your own garden B. Salad/raw vegetables from the market C. Fruit from your own garden D. Fruit from the market	Never Less than once a week About once a week Several times a week Daily
65	How often do household members eat the following?	Never Less than once a week

	A. Fresh milk from cow/sheep/goat B. Street food (prepared food or snacks)	About once a week Several times a week Daily
66	Which market do you get the salad/raw veg from?	
67	Which market do you get the fruit from?	
68	How do you prepare raw foods before eating?	Eat straight from the market Wash with drinking water before eating Peel skin before eating Wash hands before eating Other (specify)
69	Where do you get the meat from?	
70	Do you use human manure on your garden?	Never Sometimes All the time
71	Do you use animal manure or fertilizer on your garden?	Never Sometimes All the time
72	What do you do with the animal waste?	Nothing Use it as manure Put it in the refuse pit Sweep it into the bush Other (specify)
73	How do members of this household normally eat?	Shared plates Separate plates
74	What age do children in your house start drinking water?	Less than 3 months 3 – 6 months Over 6 months
75	What age do children start eating solid food in your house?	Less than 3 months 3 – 6 months Over 6 months
76	How do children under 1 year eat?	Self-feeding with hands Self-feeding with spoon Hand feeding (mother) Hand feeding (other caregiver) Other
Section 5: Household Health Seeking Behaviour		
77	Where do members of the household usually seek care in case of illness?	Tertiary Referral Hospital Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private)

		Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Family or Friend CHAM facility Self-treat with left over drugs Other (specify) Nowhere
78	Where do members of the household usually seek care in case of diarrhoea?	Tertiary Referral Hospital Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Family or Friend CHAM facility Self-treat with left over drugs Other (specify) Nowhere
79	Where do members of the household usually seek care in case of fever?	Tertiary Referral Hospital Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Family or Friend CHAM facility Self-treat with left over drugs Other (specify) Nowhere
80	Where do members of the household usually seek care if they have a persistent cough?	Tertiary Referral Hospital Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Family or Friend CHAM facility Self-treat with left over drugs Other (specify) Nowhere

81	Where do members of the household usually seek care if they were severely ill?	Tertiary Referral Hospital Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Family or Friend CHAM facility Self-treat with left over drugs Other (specify) Nowhere
Section 6: Household Experience of Illness and Antibiotics		
82	Have all members of the household completed the individual questionnaires?	Yes (go to Q85) No
82a	Is anyone in the house unwell at present or has been unwell in the last 4 weeks (that has not completed an individual questionnaire)?	Yes No (go to Q83)
82b	How many people have been unwell?	
<i>Complete questions 82bi-82bv for each individual</i>		
82bi	Now I would like to ask you about the member of the house who has been unwell in the last 4 weeks. What were they unwell with?	Fever Diarrhoea Cough/cold Sore throat Skin infection Urinary Tract Infection / dysuria Malaria (RDT confirmed only) TB (Confirmed /presumed) Brain infection (Meningitis / encephalitis) Blood stream infection Other infection (specify) Non-infectious cause (specify)
82bii	Where did they go for care?	Referral Hospital (QECH) Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Family or Friend

		CHAM facility Self-treat with left over drugs Other (specify) Nowhere
82biii	Did they get antibiotics?	Yes No (go to Q83)
82biv	What antibiotics did they get?	Amoxicillin Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid Ampicillin Ampicillin + Cloxacillin Azithromycin Benzathine benzylpenicillin Benzylpenicillin Cefalexin/Cephalexin Cefixime Ceftriaxone Cefuroxime Chloramphenicol Ciprofloxacin Clarithromycin Clindamycin Cloxacillin Cotrimoxazole (Sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim) Doxycycline Erythromycin Flucloxacillin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Metronidazole Ofloxacin Phenoxymethylpenicillin Tetracycline Tinidazole Other (specify) Unknown
82bv	What form was the antibiotic?	Tablet Capsule Syrup Suspension Injection Don't Know
83	Has anyone in the household been unwell in the last 3 months (who has not completed an individual questionnaire)	Yes No (go to Q84)
83a	How many people have been unwell?	

<i>Complete questions 83b-83bv for each individual</i>		
83bi	<p>Now I would like to ask you about the member of the house who has been unwell in the last 3 months.</p> <p>What were they unwell with?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fever Diarrhoea Cough/cold Sore throat Skin infection Urinary Tract Infection / dysuria Malaria (RDT confirmed only) TB (Confirmed /presumed) Brain infection (Meningitis / encephalitis) Blood stream infection Other infection (specify) Non-infectious cause (specify)
83bii	Where did they go for care?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Referral Hospital (QECH) Other hospital (gov) Other hospital (private) Health centre (gov) Health centre (private) Pharmacy (gov) Private pharmacy / drug store Traditional medical house Family or Friend CHAM facility Self-treat with left over drugs Other (specify) Nowhere
83biii	Did they get antibiotics?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes No (go to Q84)
83biv	What antibiotics did they get?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amoxicillin Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid Ampicillin Ampicillin + Cloxacillin Azithromycin Benzathine benzylpenicillin Benzylpenicillin Cefalexin/Cephalexin Cefixime Ceftriaxone Cefuroxime Chloramphenicol Ciprofloxacin Clarithromycin Clindamycin Cloxacillin Cotrimoxazole (Sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim)

		Doxycycline Erythromycin Flucloxacillin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Metronidazole Ofloxacin Phenoxyethylpenicillin Tetracycline Tinidazole Other (specify) Unknown
83bv	What form was the antibiotic?	Tablet Capsule Syrup Suspension Injection Don't Know
84	Has any member of the household other than yourself taken antibiotics for any other reason in the last 3 months (who has not completed an individual questionnaire)?	Yes No (go to Q85)
84a	How many people took antibiotics for any other reason in the last 3 months?	
<i>Complete questions 84b-84bi for each individual</i>		
84b	Now I would like to ask you about the member of the house who has been taking antibiotics. What antibiotics did they get?	Amoxicillin Amoxicillin + clavulanic acid Ampicillin Ampicillin + Cloxacillin Azithromycin Benzathine benzylpenicillin Benzylpenicillin Cefalexin/Cephalexin Cefixime Ceftriaxone Cefuroxime Chloramphenicol Ciprofloxacin Clarithromycin Clindamycin Cloxacillin Cotrimoxazole (Sulfamethoxazole + trimethoprim)

		Doxycycline Erythromycin Flucloxacillin Gentamicin Levofloxacin Metronidazole Ofloxacin Phenoxyethylpenicillin Tetracycline Tinidazole Other (specify) Unknown
84bi	What form was the antibiotic?	Tablet Capsule Syrup Suspension Injection Don't Know
Section 7: Animal Husbandry		
85	Do you or anyone in your household keep any animals?	Yes No (go to Q119)
86	What animals are kept?	Beef Cattle Dairy Cattle Goat Sheep Pigs Chickens Equines Dogs Doves Guinea fowl Turkeys Ducks Cats Other (specify)
87	How many of each species are owned?	
88	Where are the animals kept? (Answer for each animal species) A. Cattle B. Goats C. Sheep D. Pigs E. Chickens F. Other poultry G. Equines	In the house Shelter /Boma within household compound Shelter /Boma outside the household compound Sometimes in the house, sometimes in the compound Free roaming Other (specify)

	H. Dogs I. Other	
89	Who has the main responsibility for the animals? (Answer for each animal species) A. Cattle B. Goats C. Sheep D. Pigs E. Chickens F. Other poultry G. Equines H. Dogs I. Other	Household head Household family member Relative not from the household Friend Employee Other (specify)
90	Characteristics of livestock production system? (Answer for each animal species) A. Cattle B. Small Ruminants C. Equines D. Poultry E. Pigs F. Other animals	Zero Grazing Fenced individual farm grazing Communal Grazing Pastoral Free range Tethered Housed Semi-free range (combination of housed and free range)
91	Do you sell milk?	Yes No (go to Q92)
91a	Which period of the year do you regularly sell milk?	January February March April May June July August September October November December
92	Do you sell eggs	Yes No (go to Q93)
92a	Which period of the year do you regularly sell eggs?	January February March April May June July August

		September October November December
93	Do you sell live animals?	Yes No (go to Q94)
93a	What animals do you sell?	Cattle Goat Sheep Pigs Chickens Equines Dogs Doves Guinea fowl Turkeys Ducks Cats Other (specify)
93b	Which time of year do you sell live animals?	January February March April May June July August September October November December
94	What are the manure management used for household animals? (Answer for each animal species) A. Cattle B. Small Ruminants C. Equines D. Poultry E. Pigs F. Other animals	Do nothing (i.e., leave where passed) Discard into environment Open air Used as fertilizer yourself Sold for cash Taken by other farmers or people Other (specify)
95	What are the feed products used in household animals? (Answer for each animal species) A. Cattle B. Small Ruminants C. Equines D. Poultry	Pasture /Scavenging Waste (household /restaurant etc) Grains / crop residues Feed mixed at farm Commercial / pre-mix feeds Other (specify)

	E. Pigs F. Other animals	
Section 8: Animal Health and Disease Prevention		
96	What was the main animal disease problem during the last 12 months? (please prompt for clinical signs, and answer for each animal species) A. Cattle B. Small Ruminants C. Equines D. Poultry E. Pigs F. Other animals	Respiratory illness / cough Digestive tract illness / diarrhoea Reproductive illness / abortion / stillbirth Sudden Death Skin disease / wounds External parasites Neurological signs Other (specify)
97	Have any of your animals been sick in the last 2 weeks?	Yes No (go to Q98)
97a	Which animals have been sick?	Cattle Goat Sheep Pigs Poultry Equines Other animals
97b	What kind of disease did the animals have? (Answer for each animal species) A. Cattle B. Goat C. Sheep D. Pigs E. Poultry F. Equines G. Other animals	Respiratory illness / cough Digestive tract illness / diarrhoea Reproductive illness / abortion / stillbirth Sudden Death Skin disease / wounds External parasites Neurological signs Other (specify)
97c	Was the disease diagnosed by yourself?	Yes No (go to Q98)
97ci	If not, by whom was it diagnosed?	Veterinarian Para-Veterinarian / assistant veterinarian officer Other animal health care provider Don't know the level of training or qualification
98	From the drug categories shown, how often have you used them for CATTLE in the last 2 months? A. Vaccines	Everyday Several days a week Once a week A few times a month

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> B. Anthelmintics (albendazole etc) C. Acaricides (ectoparasites) D. Tetracyclines E. Sulphonamides F. Penicillin (and combinations) G. Fluoroquinolones H. Macrolides I. Aminoglycosides J. Other antibiotics (specify) K. Vitamins/ iron supplements L. Other drugs (specify) 	
99	<p>From the drug categories shown, how often have you used them for GOATS in the last 2 months?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Vaccines B. Anthelmintics (albendazole etc) C. Acaricides (ectoparasites) D. Tetracyclines E. Sulphonamides F. Penicillin (and combinations) G. Fluoroquinolones H. Macrolides I. Aminoglycosides J. Other antibiotics (specify) K. Vitamins/ iron supplements L. Other drugs (specify) 	<p>Everyday Several days a week Once a week A few times a month</p>
100	<p>From the drug categories shown, how often have you used them for SHEEP in the last 2 months?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Vaccines B. Anthelmintics (albendazole etc) C. Acaricides (ectoparasites) D. Tetracyclines E. Sulphonamides F. Penicillin (and combinations) G. Fluoroquinolones H. Macrolides I. Aminoglycosides J. Other antibiotics (specify) K. Vitamins/ iron supplements L. Other drugs (specify) 	<p>Everyday Several days a week Once a week A few times a month</p>
101	<p>From the drug categories shown, how often have you used them for PIGS in the last 2 months?</p>	<p>Everyday Several days a week Once a week</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Vaccines B. Anthelmintics (albendazole etc) C. Acaricides (ectoparasites) D. Tetracyclines E. Sulphonamides F. Penicillin (and combinations) G. Fluoroquinolones H. Macrolides I. Aminoglycosides J. Other antibiotics (specify) K. Vitamins/ iron supplements L. Other drugs (specify) 	A few times a month
102	<p>From the drug categories shown, how often have you used them for POULTRY in the last 2 months?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Vaccines B. Anthelmintics (albendazole etc) C. Acaricides (ectoparasites) D. Tetracyclines E. Sulphonamides F. Penicillin (and combinations) G. Fluoroquinolones H. Macrolides I. Aminoglycosides J. Other antibiotics (specify) K. Vitamins/ iron supplements L. Other drugs (specify) 	<p>Everyday</p> <p>Several days a week</p> <p>Once a week</p> <p>A few times a month</p>
103	<p>From the drug categories shown, how often have you used them for EQUINES in the last 2 months?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Vaccines B. Anthelmintics (albendazole etc) C. Acaricides (ectoparasites) D. Tetracyclines E. Sulphonamides F. Penicillin (and combinations) G. Fluoroquinolones H. Macrolides I. Aminoglycosides J. Other antibiotics (specify) K. Vitamins/ iron supplements L. Other drugs (specify) 	<p>Everyday</p> <p>Several days a week</p> <p>Once a week</p> <p>A few times a month</p>
104	<p>From the drug categories shown, how often have you used them for</p>	<p>Everyday</p> <p>Several days a week</p>

	<p>OTHER ANIMALS in the last 2 months?</p> <p>A. Vaccines</p> <p>B. Anthelmintics (albendazole etc)</p> <p>C. Acaricides (ectoparasites)</p> <p>D. Tetracyclines</p> <p>E. Sulphonamides</p> <p>F. Penicillin (and combinations)</p> <p>G. Fluoroquinolones</p> <p>H. Macrolides</p> <p>I. Aminoglycosides</p> <p>J. Other antibiotics (specify)</p> <p>K. Vitamins/ iron supplements</p> <p>L. Other drugs (specify)</p>	<p>Once a week</p> <p>A few times a month</p>
Animal Disease Problems Response		
105	<p>What do you do in response to animal disease problems? (Answer for each animal species)</p> <p>A. Cattle</p> <p>B. Goat</p> <p>C. Sheep</p> <p>D. Pigs</p> <p>E. Poultry</p> <p>F. Equines</p> <p>G. Other animals</p>	<p>Use traditional medicine</p> <p>Use medicine from the veterinary drug store</p> <p>Consult traditional healer</p> <p>Consult private veterinarian</p> <p>Consult governmental veterinarian</p> <p>Vet applied/ left drugs</p> <p>Other (please specify)</p>
106	<p>How do you protect your animals from disease? (Answer for each animal species)</p> <p>A. Cattle</p> <p>B. Goat</p> <p>C. Sheep</p> <p>D. Pigs</p> <p>E. Poultry</p> <p>F. Equines</p> <p>G. Other animals</p>	<p>Fencing</p> <p>Not mixing with other animals/herd/ flock</p> <p>Special feed / supplemental feed</p> <p>Vet drugs (in vaccine)</p> <p>Other (specify)</p> <p>Do nothing</p>
Section 9: Animal Health Services		
107	Do you have access to professional animal health services?	<p>Yes</p> <p>No (go to Q108)</p>
107a	Which one?	<p>State or Government</p> <p>Private</p> <p>Both State/ Private</p> <p>Other (specify)</p>
107b	What provider?	

107c	If you have access to health services, do the animal services include laboratory testing?	Yes No (go to 107d)
107ci	If you have access to laboratory testing, do you use it?	Yes when needed Rarely No (go to 107ciii)
107cii	For diagnosis in which species?	Cattle Goat Sheep Pigs Poultry Equines Other animals
107ciii	If you don't use them, why?	Not available Not efficient Too expensive Would like more Other (specify)
108	Is the household involved in a regular animal health program, like vaccination campaign run by the WHO / NGO?	Yes No (go to Q109)
108a	If Yes, what?	
109	Do you access pharmaceuticals /veterinary drugs?	Yes No (go to Q110)
109b	If Yes, what?	Vaccines Anthelmintics (albendazole etc) Acaricides (ectoparasites) Tetracyclines Sulphonamides Penicillin (and combinations) Fluoroquinolones Macrolides Aminoglycosides Other antibiotics (specify) Vitamins/ iron supplements Other drugs (specify)
Section 10: Drug Usage in Household Animals		
110	In your household animals, which of the drugs is most commonly used?	Vaccines Anthelmintics (albendazole etc) Arachnicides (ectoparasites) Tetracyclines Sulphonamides Penicillin (and combinations) Fluoroquinolones

		Macrolides Aminoglycosides Other antibiotics (specify) Vitamins/ iron supplements Other drugs (specify)
111	Why do you use this drug?	Routine disease prevention Treatment of sick animal Fattening / increasing animal growth To prevent disease in healthy animals when one animal of the same species is sick Other (specify)
112	Via which channel do you access this drug?	Private vet Public / official vet Animal health worker Veterinary drug store Human pharmacy Markets Feed providers Farmers Via NGOs Other (specify)
113	Which animals do you give this drug to?	All of the same species Sick animals only Sick (and in contact) animals Before selling the animal New animals introduced to the household All animals in the household
114	How long do you use this drug?	As advised Until animal(s) cured Until package empty As long as I can afford One-time treatment Continuously over extended period
115	Who administers it?	Household member Vet (or VAO) Other (specify)
116	How is the drug applied/ given?	Injection Oral With feed With water On Skin Other (specify)
117	Do you get advice about how to use the drugs?	Yes No (go to Q118)
117a	If yes, via which channel?	From the vet

		From animal health workers From pharmacies or markets From farmers or other households Via the feed provider From the package label Own judgement Other (specify)
118	When using veterinary drugs, whose instructions do you follow (for dose, length of treatment)?	The vet's The animal health worker's The Pharmacy's The feed company's Farmers or other households My own judgement? Other's (specify)
Section 11: Use of Antibiotics in Animals		
119	What do vaccines do?	Cure sick animals Prevent animals from becoming sick Cure sick animals and prevent them from becoming sick Fattening / increased growth Unsure
120	What do antibiotics do?	Cure sick animals Prevent animals from becoming sick Cure sick animals and prevent them from becoming sick Fattening / increased growth Unsure
121	Do you consume milk from animals who were recently treated with antibiotics?	Yes (go to Q122) No
121a	If no, how long before you would (in days)?	
122	Do you consume eggs from animals who were recently treated with antibiotics?	Yes (go to Q123) No
122a	If no, how long before you would (in days)?	
123	Do you consume meat from animals who were recently treated with antibiotics?	Yes (go to Q124) No
123a	If no, how long before you would (in days)?	
124	Have you experienced situations where animal drugs did not work?	Yes, frequently Yes, sometimes No (go to Q125)

124a	If you have had experience with failure, please state the drug and the animal in which it did not work?	
125	What do you do with animal drugs that have passed their expiry date?	Dispose of them Return to pharmacy Give to another household or farmer Use for intended treatment Sell Other (specify) Nothing
126	In CATTLE, what was your total expenditure on drugs during the last year (in local currency)? A. Dewormer B. Antiprotozoal C. Vaccination D. Antibiotics E. Ectoparasites F. Vitamins	
127	In GOATS, what was your total expenditure on drugs during the last year (in local currency)? A. Dewormer B. Antiprotozoal C. Vaccination D. Antibiotics E. Ectoparasites F. Vitamins	
128	In SHEEP, what was your total expenditure on drugs during the last year (in local currency)? A. Dewormer B. Antiprotozoal C. Vaccination D. Antibiotics E. Ectoparasites F. Vitamins	
129	In PIGS, what was your total expenditure on drugs during the last year (in local currency)? A. Dewormer B. Antiprotozoal C. Vaccination D. Antibiotics E. Ectoparasites F. Vitamins	

130	In POULTRY, what was your total expenditure on drugs during the last year (in local currency)? A. Dewormer B. Antiprotozoal C. Vaccination D. Antibiotics E. Ectoparasites F. Vitamins	
131	In EQUINES, what was your total expenditure on drugs during the last year (in local currency)? A. Dewormer B. Antiprotozoal C. Vaccination D. Antibiotics E. Ectoparasites F. Vitamins	
132	In OTHER ANIMALS, what was your total expenditure on drugs during the last year (in local currency)? A. Dewormer B. Antiprotozoal C. Vaccination D. Antibiotics E. Ectoparasites F. Vitamins	
133	You have completed data collection for this participant. Please thank them for their time.	
134	Staff signature	
135	Time and Date	MM:HH DD/MM/YYYY